

1 **Cas9 from Campylobacter jejuni.**

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8 We present here genetic evidence collected from cells demonstrating functional capacity of the Cas9
9 enzyme from Campylobacter jejuni in genomic editing and gene expression regulatory applications.

10 Citations

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